

TECHNICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CHALLENGES FOR IMPLEMENTING FEEDBACK STRATEGIES IN A VIRTUAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

Asima Iqbal

WMG, University of Warwick
Coventry, UK

Maryam Masood

WMG, University of Warwick
Coventry, UK
0000-0002-4073-2105

Lauren Schrock¹

WMG, University of Warwick
Coventry, UK

Ninna Makrinov

WMG, University of Warwick
Coventry, UK

Conference Key Areas: *Student Engagement, Navigating Open Learning Environments*

Keywords: *Automatic feedback, Peer feedback, Tutor-led feedback, Virtual learning environments*

ABSTRACT

Pedagogical developments in the virtual learning environment (VLE) are constrained by technical expertise which impacts the design and delivery of online learning, including the implementation of varied feedback strategies. In recognising this dilemma, the paper addresses the question, “*What are the technical and pedagogical challenges of implementing feedback strategies in a VLE?*” This short paper presents an initial critical, reflexive account on the challenges to embed and manage feedback strategies, including automatic feedback, peer feedback, and tutor-led feedback, on the VLE of a blended module provided to over 1,200 engineering and business students at a UK university. As a result, the authors recognise the importance of upskilling engineering educators to technically innovate

¹ *Corresponding Author*

Lauren Schrock

Lauren.Schrock@warwick.ac.uk

their VLEs to enhance student learning and connections through feedback. Further investigations to evaluate the impact of the varied feedback strategies on student learning will occur at a later stage in order to advance this work in progress.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 pandemic has renewed interest in the development of feedback practices in a virtual learning environment (VLE) [1]. Yet engineering educators face barriers to implement a variety of feedback strategies, including automatic feedback, peer feedback, and tutor-led feedback, in online learning spaces. Therefore, this short paper addresses the question, *“What are the technical and pedagogical challenges of implementing feedback strategies in a VLE?”*

Feedback is important for student learning, because it can “raise students’ consciousness of the strengths of their work, boost students’ confidence and self-concept regarding personal strengths and abilities, provide guidance on areas for further development of skills and enhancement of work, [and] enhance students’ own judgement, understanding of assessment criteria and ability to self-audit their own work” [2]. In addition, embedding a variety of feedback strategies is significant for curating a dynamic environment that facilitates flexible learning, individualisation, and connection. However, pedagogical justifications for feedback are compromised by a feasibility to manage resourcing of feedback provision and a technical ability to implement different feedback strategies. This is the case for the design of a VLE for a blended module on transferrable skills and research methods provided to over 1,200 postgraduate engineering and business students at a UK university.

The scope of the paper is on the feedback strategies implemented on formative learning activities embedded in the module’s VLE. These activities are accessible to over 1,200 postgraduate students across 20 unique sessions delivered on a weekly basis. The activities were created and managed by the four authors who form the module teaching team. This high student-to-teacher ratio is a constraint that intensified the challenges of pedagogical and technical design and delivery of feedback.

This short paper is a reflexive account by the authors on facing and resolving challenges to embed varied feedback strategies in a VLE for a large student cohort. By presenting initial findings that interrogate the tension between pedagogy and technology, this work in progress provides initial suggestions for engineering educators who seek to innovate their VLE and enhance student learning.

2 METHODOLOGY FOR PROVIDING FEEDBACK IN A VLE

Five feedback strategies were employed on the VLE of the module. These include: (1) *'No virtual feedback'* for activities in which feedback was delivered outside of the VLE (e.g. a poll to engage students to see how their responses compare with other students). Another strategy was automatic feedback, or when feedback was provided immediately following the completion of an activity, and was divided into two categories. (2) *'Automatic feedback – quiz'* is contrasted with (3) *'Automatic feedback – response available'*, as the former is individualised feedback based on incorrect responses while the latter is a 'good example' provided to students after activity submission to enable critical comparison. (4) *'Peer feedback'* includes forum activities in which students respond to other students' posts. This enables student learning communities to form online. Finally, (5) *'Tutor-led feedback'* is the provision of personal feedback on an activity by a member of the teaching team. This is important for creating connections between students and staff. Since the focus of this short paper is on feedback strategies in a VLE, *'No virtual feedback'* will not be discussed here. Nonetheless it is significant since in a blended module, feedback is also provided in a synchronous, face-to-face environment.

Each feedback strategy had its own unique benefits to support the different learning needs of students and enable connections between student and student, or student and teacher. Further, different feedback strategies may be more sustainable considering tutor workload at a time during module delivery. For instance, during an intensive work period in which the teaching team was reduced from four to two individuals, it was only feasible to provide automatic feedback since there was no flexibility to provide or technically support alternative forms of feedback.

To account for the number of feedback strategies employed on the module VLE, a frequency analysis is presented in Table 1, below. There were 85 formative learning activities on the VLE split across 20 asynchronous sessions. All 1,200 students could access these activities, though not all students completed them since only some of these students completed the module for credit. The number of activities varied across sessions; this caused concern about student workload. Hence, in response to mid-module feedback, the number of formative activities decreased for sessions 15-19 to enable deeper learning and higher engagement. Consequently, the number of opportunities for feedback on formative learning activities was also reduced as a result of this change in response to mid-module feedback.

Table 1. Feedback strategies employed in the module VLE

Feedback Strategies					
	<i>No virtual feedback</i>	<i>Automatic feedback -</i>	<i>Automatic feedback –</i>	<i>Peer feedback</i>	<i>Tutor-led feedback</i>

		<i>quiz</i>	<i>response available</i>			
No. of activities	16	47	15	6	1	N = 85 (100%)

It is noticeable that '*Automatic feedback – quiz*' appears more often than other forms of feedback. This reflects the over-reliance of the teaching team on one form of feedback due to the technical ease of using an online quiz to provide feedback on student learning. In contrast, '*Tutor-led feedback*' did not occur frequently due to concerns that marking individual submissions and providing personalised feedback to scale would compromise the workload of the team while removing flexibility of student learning by imposing a deadline for submission.

3 CHALLENGES TO IMPLEMENTING FEEDBACK STRATEGIES IN A VLE

3.1 Balancing pedagogy, workload and technical ability

In analysing the reflexive accounts of the teaching team, a key dilemma to implementing various feedback strategies was balancing pedagogical design with academic workload and technical ability. For instance, a challenge of tutor-led feedback was managing the high student-to-teacher ratio on an online platform. While there are technical solutions for reducing feedback administration time, such as embedding a standard rubric to the VLE or viewing student submissions online rather than downloading, providing individual feedback en masse severely compromised the workload of the team. While a justification can be made for generating feedback by artificial intelligence [3], the extreme workload to provide individual, tutor-led feedback in the absence of technical confidence supported the design of *blended* learning in which synchronous, face-to-face seminars, drop-in sessions, and office hours offered the opportunity for tutor-led feedback.

The lack of technical ability by the team meant there was limited use of software and applications to create multiple modes in which feedback was communicated to enable students to select feedback relevant to their skill level and/or learning style. For instance, the team frequently utilised automatic feedback that was relayed in standardised text. This meant it was not possible to alter the vocabulary or meaning of the feedback to ensure it was understood by all students [4]. Therefore, upskilling educators on how to create and embed automatic feedback in creative ways, such as audio and/or video recordings, and pitched at different levels of knowledge, can enable students to select how they best learn [5].

3.2 Problematising student learning and connection

To support student learning, it is important that students engage and learn from feedback. However, in an online environment where students can move freely through activities, it is possible that students are not engaging deeply. For instance, in analysing the data on the time duration taken to complete a quiz, the tutors identified students who purposely failed a quiz to quickly receive the correct answers, so these can be inputted as fast as possible in order to complete the activity. Technical design can resolve this by reducing the number of attempts available to pass a quiz. Yet, while it appears students are moving quickly through activities as part of surface learning, there is no data available on how students engaged with the feedback. For instance, it was not clear if students moved quickly through the activity to spend more time with the feedback in order to learn from 'correct' or 'good' answers or how students applied this feedback to their future learning and practice. Hence, this work in progress plans to undertake further evaluations to explore student literacy of feedback in a VLE, as well as the unique influence of each feedback strategy on student learning [6].

Peer feedback is a means to develop virtual learning communities and a sense of belonging through frequent interactions that build student connections. This is important since students with a higher sense of belonging are more motivated to engage and learn, and therefore achieve [7]. Yet these positive outcomes were undermined by a lack of technical ability of the teaching team to create multiple small groups of students. As a result, each forum was shared by all students; this weakened the formation of meaningful and stable student connections due to the large class size. Therefore, technical upskilling also concerns an ability to manipulate organisational settings of the VLE, such as establishing unique user groups that exist across peer activities, to improve student connections.

Furthermore, while guidance was provided to students on how to give peer feedback on posts, this did not mean the guidance was followed, since forums are assessed on participation and not learning. To overcome this technical challenge, a pedagogical solution is to provide a marking checklist or rubric to enable depth and consistency to peer marking that can be embedded in the VLE for common use. This can enhance learning since expectations to the application, analysis, and evaluation of knowledge in the activity are clarified for students.

4 CONCLUSION

This short paper provides a reflexive, critical account of technical and pedagogical challenges to implement varied feedback strategies in the VLE for a module with a high student-to-teacher ratio. A key theme is the need to upskill educators on the technical capabilities of VLEs and use of accompanying software and applications,

so the design of feedback is based on pedagogical innovation rather than technical comfort. For instance, resolving the team's over-reliance on text-based automatic feedback by ensuring time is made available for prototyping and testing feedback strategies so they can be embedded within the learning design. Enhancing the technical skills of engineering educators to innovate their VLE would benefit students' deeper learning. Also, in the case of this transferrable skills and research methods module, it would improve the quality of the learning experience, so students do not spend most of their time applying their knowledge in independent activities that receive monologic feedback.

Furthermore, greater consideration must be made to sustainable feedback that does not compromise the workload of the teaching team and students. Hence, when testing feedback strategies in a VLE, it is important to consider the time needed to create and disseminate feedback, particularly in regard to the quantity and quality of feedback provided to students throughout the module. Also, the decision to use one feedback strategy over another will be made following further evaluation of student preferences for, and impact of, different feedback strategies on student learning in the VLE. Therefore, this work in progress will extend these initial suggestions through further evaluation of the online feedback strategies on student learning and connections in order to advance engineering education.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hast, M (2020), Higher Education in Times of Covid-19: Giving Online Feedback Implementation Another Look, *Higher Education Studies*, Vol. 11, No. 1, pp. 1-7.
- [2] The Higher Education Academy (2013), HEA Feedback toolkit, The Higher Education Academy, Heslington, p. 8. Available at: https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/assets.creode.advancehe-document-manager/documents/hea/private/resources/feedback_toolkit_whole1_1568036614.pdf [Accessed 15/07/2022].
- [3] Zawack-Richter, O, Marin, V I, Bond, M, and Gouverneur, F (2019), Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education – where are the educators?, *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, Vol. 16, No. 39, pp. 16-39.
- [4] Pinheiro Cavalcanti, A, Barbosa, A, Carvalho, R, Freitas, F, Tsai, Y, Gasevic, D, and Ferreira Mello, R (2021), Automatic feedback in online learning environments: A systematic literature review. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, Vol. 2, pp. 1-17.
- [5] Pitt, E and Winstone, N (2020), Towards Technology Enhanced Dialogic Feedback. In: Bearman, M, Dawson, P, Ajjawi, R., Tai, J, Boud, D (eds), Re-imagining University Assessment in A Digital World, The Enabling Power of Assessment, Vol. 7, Springer, pp. 79-94.
- [6] Wood, J (2021), A dialogic technology-mediated model of feedback uptake and literacy, *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, Vol. 46, No. 8,

pp.1173-1190.

- [7] Pedler M L, Willis, R, and Nieuwoudt, J E (2022), A sense of belonging at university: student retention, motivation and enjoyment, *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, Vol. 46, No. 3, pp. 397-408.